

Consumer perception regarding LIC during COVID-19 pandemic

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Abstract:

The COVID-19 pandemic and lockdown have impacted almost all the industries and sectors across the world including the insurance sector which has a significant contribution in the country's GDP and economic development. This paper is an attempt to study the effect of COVID-19 pandemic and its overall effect on consumer perception regarding Indian life insurance sector. The study is exploratory in nature and thus give new insight to related future researches. In order to conduct the study, the secondary data has been collected from various newspaper articles, online blogs, website and annual report of LIC and IRDA. The paper covers various dimensions like first total premium of LIC, No. of lives covered under the schemes, No. of policies issued and also make an effort to analyse the overall performance of life insurance company in FY 2011 to FY 2021. The period of study covered ten years i.e pre and post COVID. The findings of the study reveals that COVID-19 has adversely affects the life insurance business mainly in term of drop down in sales of new policy, premium income and crises of claim settlement. The experts view that the demand of pure and health insurance has been shown a positive growth due to life uncertainties in times of COVID-19 pandemic.

Keywords: Life insurance sector, COVID-19 pandemic and its impact, Business and performance of LIC

Introduction:

The business of insurance is related to the protection of the economic values of the assets. Every human being has the tendency to save to protect him from risks or events of future. Insurance is one form of savings where in people try to assure themselves against risks or uncertainties of future.it is assurance agaist risks or events or losses. Coronavirus disease, scientifically reclassified as COVID-19, has assumed global pandemic proportions. It attained a pandemic status declared by the World Health Organisation (WHO) on 11th march 2020. The spread of this virus at the fast rate compare to previous pandemic has resulted in a total lockdown of nation, ban to travels, public gathering and closure of offices. There has been

global closure of businesses as well as the loss of jobs and lives. The general economic situation is a global recession. In most instances, the insurance industry and governments all over the world have become the be cons of hope to which people look for rescue from total annihilation. However due to fast increase in infection cases greater than the recovery of infected people, the pandemic has overwhelmed many governments and financially weakened some insurance companies. The impact of the pandemic on the Indian insurance industry is yet to be estimated and projected to provide a guide for government and insurers for the simulation of future events. The COVID-19 crises continues to have a significant impact on individuals, society, business and the wider economy across the globe.

The insurance industry has not escaped its impact but insurers have responded quickly to the crisis as the broader economy recovers and responds to the pandemic insurers will face a number of challenges but also see many new opportunities in the medium to long term.

Literature Review:

A comprehensive review of related past studies helps the researcher to adopt, modify and improve the conceptualization of framework and provide a link with past approaches. The findings and recommendation of the past literature relating to COVID-19 are not many. Based on the review of literature the researcher has able to identify her source for the present study. The available studies are collected from research articles, committee reports, projects and surveys conducted.

Ramakrishna Reddy and Raghunadha Reddy (2000) attempt to study the issues and relate conclusion on certain matters like whether premium rates reflect the life expectancy or the policy designed only for government employees or semi government employees or reputed commercial firms etc. The spirit of the policyholders to know about the working, drawbacks and short comings of the Life Insurance Company is discussed. The study reveals that the rates of premium charged under postal life insurance are less and cheaper compared to the rates of premium of Life Insurance Company. As it is covered for a confined class of selective masses, it is felt necessary to concentrate on uncovered areas and non-salaried class as potential Market segments. The foremost change required is to provide transparency of information to the community, as they have the freedom to access any information about the working of Company.

Agarwal, R.F. (2001) has attempted to study the importance of information technology in the insurance industry and brings out the efficient

need of providing improved services when there is competition due to private entry. In an insurance company, the service of it may be utilized in many areas like customer service, claim management, human resources etc. It is assumed that to have an overall increase in the size of the insurance market, information technology must be used on a much vigorous basis for more extensive penetration.

V. V. Narsi Reddy, Marulu Reddy, Seelam (2019) in this paper an attempt is made to study the financial performance and investment performance of life insurance corporation of india ltd and also to examine financial performance, income, outgo and their sub- components are chosen. This paper is divided into two sections.

S. Udhaya Kumar, D. Thirumal Kumar, B. Prabhu Christopher And C. George Priya Doss (2020)

This article is entitled the rise and impact of covid -19 in India . the coronavirus disease (COVID-19) pandemic which originated in the city of Wuhan, china has quickly spread to various countries with many cases having been reported worldwide as well as in India.

Research Methodology:

The present study is new and thus researcher used exploratory research design in order to study the effect of COVID-19 on life insurance sector in India. The study is based on qualitative research approach Hoepfel (1997) used to gain new perspectives on issues where little literature is known. Secondary data was obtained from various IRDA reports, websites, online reviews and newspapers, articles and blogs. Content analysis was used to conduct this study as researcher movement were restricted due to COVID-19 pandemic situation.

Data Analysis and Interpretation:

The present study is purely secondary based. The period of study is confined to 10 years that is 2011 to 2021. Researcher has collected data of April 2011 to March 2021. This study utilized the hand collected data of LIC and COVID position in Maharashtra. Here the years 2011 to 2019 are consider to pre COVID pandemic and the year 2020 and 2021 are consider during and post COVID pandemic situation. We collect our panel data quarterly for the year 2011 to 2021 based on data availability.

Objectives of Proposed Research:

1. To know the impact of COVID-19 on insurance sector.
2. To understand the importance of life insurance in human life.
3. To discuss the consumer perception regarding life insurance before and after COVID-19 pandemic and present solution.
4. To understand the changing trends and challenges in life insurance sector during COVID-19

Scope of Research Work:

Insurance business has emerged as one of the prominent areas of financial services during recent times. Insurance performance remarkable functions by insuring the insurable people and property located at different places. This study aims to investigate the impact of COVID-19 on insurance industry in India with special reference to LIC and discuss solution as well as project future expectation of human being.

Relevance of the Research Work:

Life is very important factor for human. In this pandemic death or infection cases greater than the recovery of infected people has resulted in a total lockdown of nation, ban to travels,

public gathering and closure of offices. There has been global closure of businesses as well as the loss of jobs and lives. The general economic situation is a global recession. This COVID-19 pandemic affected on local as well as global economy. It resulted into the impact on financial sector mainly on insurance sector.

Premium Income of LIC:

YEAR	LIC
2011-2012	2,02,889.28
2012-2013	2,08,803.58
2013-2014	2,36,942.30
2014-2015	2,39,667.65
2015-2016	2,66,444.21
2016-2017	3,00,487.21
2017-2018	3,18,223.20
2018-2019	3,37,185.40
2019-2020	3,79,389.60
2020-2021	4,03,286.55

Source: IRDA Annual Reports various issues from 2011-2012 to 2020-2021

It is a fact that premium considered as a major source of income of life insurers therefore it is the most important indicator of growth and performance of insurance business. The Table shows the total premium income of LIC during year 2011-12 to 2020-2021

Current Position Of COVID-19 Cases:

The first case of the COVID-19 pandemic in the Indian state of Maharashtra was confirmed on 9 March 2020. Maharashtra is a hotspot that accounts for nearly 22.35% of the total cases in India as well as about 30.55% of all deaths. As of 10 May 2021, the state's case fatality rate is nearly 1.49%. Pune is the worst-affected city in Maharashtra, with about 930,809 cases as of 10 May 2021. About half of the cases in the state emerged from the Mumbai

Metropolitan Region .The total number of cases in Maharashtra reported as of May 2022,

is **78,87,086** consisting of **1,47,860** deaths and **77,35,751** who have recovered.

Map of district with confirm cases

Map of deaths due to Covid-19

Expected outcome:

The study was conducted with the aim of describing the insurance industry performance before covid and after COVID-19 pandemic in India. The changing trends and challenges faced by life insurance providers are also been analysed under the study. To attain the stated objectives, researcher has used exploratory research design. Insurance industry plays a very crucial role in economy as it saves life, encourages investment, household's savings and also provides mass employment to youth of the nation. Together with banking sector contributes more than seven percent GDP of economy. Like other sectors of economy, insurance sector is also adversely affected with the present situation of COVID-19 pandemic mainly in terms of decline in new policy business, delayed premium payments, increase in policy lapsation and financial crises of claim settlements due to rise in number of covid pandemic. To deal with these issues, insurers need to come up with more customer-centric innovative solutions which give multiple benefits to the policyholders. During the covid-19 period, many changing trends have been observed that people get more aware with the importance of life insurance plan, significant growth in the

demand of health and pure life insurance, increased business of online insurance (Aprajita Sharma,2021) and more oriented towards customer-centric unique solutions (Henrik et al,2020). The insurance companies face liquidity problems in the short run and solvency problems in the long run if the pandemic stays for a long time. No doubt there are many hurdles for insurance companies in present tough times. But with effective policy measures, the challenges can be turned into opportunities by looking for alternative options like giving more digital services to the customers in terms of giving online policy information, policy buying, premium payment and also fast claim settlement. All customer services are available at door and insurance employees are allowed to work from home which helps to reduce company operation costs and other expenses. In the current uncertain situation where life-related risks are very high. People tend to invest in long-term insurance in order to secure their family and loved ones. Both pure insurance and health insurance come out as a great opportunity for insurance providers.

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